

On the equidistribution properties of patterns in prime numbers Jumping Champions, meta analysis of properties as Low-Discrepancy Sequences, and some conjectures based on Ramanujan's master theorem and the zeros of Riemann's zeta function

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Abstract

The Paul Erdős–Turán inequality is used as a quantitative form of Weyl's criterion, together with other criteria to assess equidistribution properties on some patterns of sequences that arise from indexation of prime numbers, Jumping Champions (called here and in previous work, "meta-distances" or even md , for short). A statistical meta-analysis is also made of previous research concerning meta-distances to review the conclusion that meta-distances can be called Low-discrepancy sequences (LDS), and thus exhibiting another numerical evidence that md 's are an equidistributed sequence. Ramanujan's master theorem is used to conjecture that the types of integrands where md 's can be used more successfully for quadratures are product-related, as opposite to addition-related. Finally, it is conjectured that the equidistribution of md 's may be connected to the known equidistribution of zeros of Riemann's zeta function, and yet still have enough "information" for quasi-random integration ("right" amount of entropy).

Keywords: Paul Erdős–Turán inequality, Low Discrepancy Sequences, Ramanujan's master theorem, zeros of Riemann's zeta function.

1. Introduction

1.1 *Jumping Champions and Metadistances*

In their paper [9] of 1999 A. Odlyzko, M. Rubinstein, and M. Wolf made the following assertion

Wolf, Odlyzko, Rubinstein Conjecture 1.2 Conjecture 1.2. The jumping champions tend to infinity. Furthermore, any fixed prime p divides all sufficiently large jumping champions. Odlyzko, Rubinstein, and Wolf 1999

the first assertion of Conjecture 1.2 was proved in 1980 by Erdős and Straus. Erdos and Straus 1980, under the assumption of the truth of the Hardy-Littlewood prime pair conjecture Hardy and Littlewood 1923.

[...] Thus, 6 may not be the Jumping champion as x tends to infinity, but according to Conjecture 1.2, it can always be possible to find 6 as a difference between two prime numbers.

Among the efforts to study the patterns within prime numbers, it is to describe the “Jumping Champions” Odlyzko, Rubinstein, and Wolf 1999 which are the most frequent differences between prime numbers, that is to say

$$\mathbb{J} = \max[P_{i+1} - P_i] \tag{1}$$

With the exception of the distance between the second and the first primes, namely, 2 and 3, all the other distances between prime numbers are even Guy 2004.

Because 6 is the jumping champion up to about $n \approx 1.74 \times 10^{35}$ Odlyzko, Rubinstein, and Wolf 1999, it was decided to investigate if the number 6 was associated systematically with other distances for subsets of this last range Ortiz-Tapia 2008b, and the exploration was performed for dyads, triads and other n -ads. Because the dyads could be found more often Ortiz-Tapia 2008b, it was decided to concentrate on them for further analysis. Out of the first one million distances between prime numbers, the dyad $\{4, 6\}$ was found 15,860 times and the dyad $\{6, 6\}$ was found 17,546 times, with diverse spacings between each dyad Ortiz-Tapia 2008b. Specifically, let the dyad $\{6, 6\}$ be formed by:

$$\{P_{i+1} - P_i, P_{i+2} - P_{i+1}\} \tag{2}$$

where this set of ‘ P ’s’ represent those prime numbers capable of generating the required dyad. The set of distances between any two dyads like $\{6, 6\}$ was found with the following observation of the indices of primes related to those dyads:

$$\overbrace{i, i+2}^j, \overbrace{i+k, i+k+2}^{j+1}, k \in \mathbf{N} \tag{3}$$

$$md = (i + k_{j+1}) - (i + k_{j+2}), md \in \mathbf{Md}$$

where md stands as shorthand for ‘meta-distances’, the way those distances were called in previous work Ortiz-Tapia 2008b, implying distances embedded in the set of distances between prime numbers, and also \mathbf{Md} is the set of all the meta-distances within a given range of prime numbers. There was a brief exploration to find a pattern within the set \mathbf{Md} , and none was found. Precisely it was the lack of apparent pattern in the meta-distances which lead to an inquiry whether they form a uniformly distributed sequence, which could be a low-discrepancy sequence, and in consequence the meta-distances could be used for multidimensional integration Ortiz-Tapia 2008b.

Several numerical tests were made using \mathbf{Md} , and also other sequences, all of them compared against the Gauss-Kronrod method implemented in Mathematica (GK) Wolfram 1999 or the analytical solution. The other sequences were created from the following generators:

- Mathematica's® Monte Carlo method of integration (MMC).
- A Monte Carlo method, using the random number generator of Mathematica (RMN) Wolfram 1999, which in turn uses the Marsaglia-Zaman subtract-with-borrow generator for real numbers Marsaglia, Zaman, and Tsang 1990
- Prime intervals or first differences of primes (PI).
- The digits of the number π (PiDi).
- The first 20,000 digits of the number $e = 2.718281 \dots$ (eDi)
- The digits of $\sqrt{71}$ (71Di).

All the numerical bases based on the digits of some number were normalized in a similar fashion to the prime meta-distances: because the maximal number in those bases is the digit 9, all of them were divided by this digit and multiplied by two. Integration was done also by a convolution Ortiz-Tapia 2008b, and was carried for different types of integrands, with different types of bounds and integrating in one or more dimensions, up to four dimensional integrands. The results were analyzed statistically using the mean and standard deviation of the relative error, whereupon **Md** resulted in $9\% \leq \bar{x} \leq 11\%$ and $2\% \leq \sigma \leq 25\%$. The integration using the other types of sequences resulted in similar variability Ortiz-Tapia 2008b.

As for the speed of convergence, almost all sequences had at least linear convergence, that is to say, suppose we have a sequence $\{x_n\}$ such that $x_n \rightarrow x_\infty$ in \mathbb{R}^k . We say the convergence is *linear* if there exists $r \in (0, 1)$

$$\frac{\|x_{n+1} - x_\infty\|}{\|x_n - x_\infty\|} \leq r \quad (4)$$

for all n sufficiently large. In fact, **Md** consistently converged with at most 15,000 evaluations of the integrand, regardless of the dimension, as opposite to all other sequences, converging with at least 20,000 integrand evaluations Ortiz-Tapia 2008b.

1.2 Leveque, Wozniakowski, and Halton theorems

In previous work Ortiz-Tapia 2008a there was some exploration of Leveque's inequality Kuipers and Niederreiter 2012, Wozniakowski's theorem Wozniakowski 1991, and Halton's theorem Halton 1960, concerning the identification of a discrepancy sequence as such. Leveque's inequality resulted in an average of $D_N \approx 0.8$, Wozniakowski's rendered $T_N^* \approx 0.2$ and Halton theorem was an average of ≈ 9 , across dimensions of integration $s \in 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7$. No comparison was made with other sequences. Both Leveque's inequality and Wozniakowski theorem agree in order of magnitude about the discrepancy of **Md**, whereas Halton theorem would agree in order of magnitude with the average error across all dimensions, which was $\bar{\epsilon} \approx 4.9$ Ortiz-Tapia 2008a. Again, no comparison was made with other sequences.

In this work new comparisons are made, and new evidence is presented for considering **Md** as an Equidistributed sequence.

2. Ramanujan's master theorem and Conjecture of types of integrand better suited for MD

In Ortiz-Tapia 2011 it was shown that kernels of "multiplicative" type of Fredholm integral equations are better suited for being solved with Low-Discrepancy Sequences,

specifically with **Md**. Multiplicative, in the sense that the kernel is composed mostly of products, as opposite of having sums inside the kernel. The reason for this numerical behavior was conjectured to be related to the higher probability of divisibility of numbers as opposite to the probability of addition. Although this conjecture was substantiated with some numerical exploration, a stronger argument can be found using Ramanujan's Master Theorem, named after Srinivasa Ramanujan Amdeberhan *et al.* 2012.

Ramanujan's Master Theorem is a technique that provides an analytic expression for the Mellin transform of an analytic function. The result is stated as follows :

Theorem 2.1 (Ramanujan's Master theorem) *If a complex-valued function $f(x)$ has an expansion of the form*

$$f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\varphi(k)}{k!} (-x)^k \quad (5)$$

then the Mellin transform of $f(x)$ is given by

$$\int_0^{\infty} x^{-s-1} f(x) dx = \Gamma(s) \varphi(-s) \quad (6)$$

Since the Gamma function (the generalized factorial) is present in this theorem, any analytic function that complies with Theorem 2.1 would be expressed as some type of product, thus it can be conjectured that **Md** solve both integrals or integral equations with integrands or kernels respectively that comply with theorem 2.1

3. Statistics

The rule of thumb seems to be: If the skewness is between -0.5 and 0.5 , the data are fairly symmetrical. If the skewness is between -1 and -0.5 or between 0.5 and 1 , the data are moderately skewed. If the skewness is less than -1 or greater than 1 , the data are highly skewed McNeese 2016. Thus, the results in Table 1 would suggest that **Md** has the most symmetrical distribution of errors.

It is also known that Positive kurtosis indicates that the data exhibit more extreme outliers than a normal distribution, negative kurtosis indicates that the data exhibit less extreme outliers than a normal distribution, and for a normal distribution, the value of the kurtosis statistic is zero Corporation 2017. Thus, under this interpretation of kurtosis, the results shown in table 1 would suggest that **Md** would exhibit the least amount of extreme outliers.

As for the Interquartile Range, the comparison shown in Fig.1 shows evidence that **Md** has the least dispersion, albeit the standard deviation of its errors shows the opposite in Table 1.

Table 1. % error (excluding outliers)

	Md	MMC	Gk / An	RMN	PI	PiDi	eDi	71 Di
average	7.6	1.0	NA	6.3	14.4	7.9	7.2	7.1
stdv	4.7	1.0	NA	8.1	11.4	9.8	9.7	9.2
skewness	-0.3	1.2	NA	1.4	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.2
Kurtosis	-1.3	1.7	NA	0.7	0.7	-0.4	-0.4	-0.2
median	8.7	0.9	NA	3.4	10.3	3.9	2.3	4.5

Figure 1. Comparison of Interquartile Range of the percentage of errors for the different sequences

4. Equidistribution Measures

4.1 Equidistribution on non-degenerate intervals

A sequence (s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots) of real numbers is said to be equidistributed on a non-degenerate interval $[a, b]$ if for every subinterval $[c, d]$ of $[a, b]$ we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\{s_1, \dots, s_n\} \cap [c, d]|}{n} = \frac{d-c}{b-a}. \quad (7)$$

(Here, the notation $|\{s_1, \dots, s_n\} \cap [c, d]|$ denotes the number of elements, out of the first n elements of the sequence, that are between c and d .) Kuipers and Niederreiter 2012

To apply Eq.4.1, the following steps were followed:

- Normalize **Md**
- Consider an interval with $size \in \{0.1, 0.2, 0.25, 0.333\}$
- measure how many subintervals (n) of **Md** fall within a given interval, such that $size \leq |Md_{k+1} - Md_k| \leq 2 \times size$
- With the previous measure, obtain the proportion of those subintervals, with respect to the length N of the entire sequence, that is, n/N .

The results are summarized in the matrix of Table 2

Table 2. Measured vs expected fraction of subintervals of **Md**

measured n/N	expected
0.0909039	0.1
0.166657	0.2
0.199989	0.25
0.249986	0.333

4.2 Well - distributed sequence

A sequence (s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots) of real numbers is said to be *well - distributed* on $[a, b]$ if for any subinterval $[c, d]$ of $[a, b]$ we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\{s_{k+1}, \dots, s_{k+n}\} \cap [c, d]|}{n} = \frac{d-c}{b-a} \quad (8)$$

uniformly in k Kuipers and Niederreiter 2012. To apply Eq.8, the following steps were followed:

- Normalize **Md**
- Consider an interval with $size \in \{0.1, 0.2, 0.25, 0.333\}$
- measure how many subintervals (n) of **Md** fall within a given interval, such that $size \leq |Md_{k+j} - Md_k| \leq 2 \times size$, where $j \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$
- With the previous measure, obtain the proportion of those subintervals, with respect to the length N of the entire sequence, that is, n/N , and for every j .

The results are summarized in Table 3

Table 3. Well-distributedness properties of \mathbf{Md} : Measured vs expected fraction of subintervals of \mathbf{Md} , with varying spacing k

k=	1	2	3	4	5	Expected
	0.0909039	0.0908987	0.0908935	0.0908884	0.0908832	0.1
	0.166657	0.166648	0.166638	0.166629	0.166619	0.2
	0.199989	0.199977	0.199966	0.199954	0.199943	0.25
	0.249986	0.249972	0.249957	0.249943	0.249929	0.333

4.3 Weyl's criterion

Weyl's criterion Kuipers and Niederreiter 2012 states that the sequence a_n is equidistributed modulo 1 if and only if for all non-zero integers ℓ

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n e^{2\pi i \ell a_j} = 0. \quad (9)$$

A quantitative form of Weyl's criterion is given by the Erdős-Turán inequality (Erdős and Turán 1948).

Let $(s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots) \in \mathbb{R}$ be a sequence. The Erdős-Turán inequality applied to the measure

$$\frac{1}{m} \#\{1 \leq j \leq m \mid s_j \bmod 1 \in S\}, \quad S \subset [0, 1), \quad (10)$$

yields the following bound for the discrepancy:

$$\begin{aligned} D(m) & \left(= \sup_{0 \leq a < b \leq 1} \left| m^{-1} \#\{1 \leq j \leq m \mid a \leq s_j \bmod 1 \leq b\} - (b-a) \right| \right) \\ & \leq C \left(\frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k} \left| \sum_{j=1}^m e^{2\pi i s_j / k} \right| \right). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

This inequality holds for arbitrary natural numbers m, n , and gives a quantitative form of Weyl's criterion for equidistribution. In Eq.4.3, $m = |\mathbf{Md}|$, and n is a natural number set up in this work to review if there is convergence.

Applying Eq.4.3, it was possible to determine that the upper bound of $\mathbf{Md} \leq 2.85$, as it is illustrated in Fig.2

To verify that the upper bound shown in Fig.2 does converge, it was calculated the difference of the successor minus the predecessor of the sequence of partial sums/upper bounds. For the purposes of illustration, that set of differences was fit into several nonlinear models of the form ax^b , for several portions of the set, to show graphically that this set of differences are likely to be a Cauchy sequence, thus convergence is guaranteed. Both the set of differences and the non-linear fits are illustrated in Fig.3

To further assess whether or not the differences form a Cauchy sequence, it was calculated the set of residuals from the different non-linear fits. A Cauchy sequence is

Figure 2. Upper bound of $Md \leq 2.85$, as a sequence of values as $m, n \rightarrow \infty$

Figure 3. Convergence of differences of upper bound for Md , together with several fits of nonlinear models of the form ax^b to illustrate these differences that seem to be a Cauchy sequence

a sequence whose terms ultimately become arbitrarily close together, after sufficiently many initial terms have been discarded, and this is the Cauchy criterion for convergence of sequences. For each $\epsilon > 0$ there are only finitely many sequence members outside the epsilon tube. Regardless which $\epsilon > 0$ we have, there is an index N_0 , so that the sequence lies afterwards completely in the epsilon tube $(a - \epsilon, a + \epsilon)$ Spivak 1994; Courant et al. 1965. That the residuals make a Cauchy sequence is presented in Fig.4

4.4 Conjecture related to the zeros of the Riemann’s zeta function

It has been proven (assuming the Riemann hypothesis) that the zeros of the Riemann’s zeta function are equidistributed Montgomery 1973. Since the zeroes of Riemann’s zeta function are a way of encoding the position of prime numbers Watkins 2023, it could be conjectured that, at least partially, this is the reason *why* Md is an equidistributed sequence.

Figure 4. Plot of residuals (the errors between the differences of partial sums and the non-linear fits of the form ax^b) showing the fulfillment of the criterion for being a Cauchy sequence, and thus the partial sums calculated using Eq.4.3 do converge.

For testing this conjecture, in Katz and Sarnak 1999 it is mentioned that the “pair correlation” of the zeroes, that they obey the laws of the Gaussian (or equivalently, Circular) Unitary Ensemble GUE. Specifically

$$r_2(GUE)(x) = 1 - \left(\frac{\sin \pi x}{\pi x} \right)^2 \quad (12)$$

Equation 4.4 is compared to the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of **MD** in Fig.5; from this figure, it was thought that a non-linear model could be fitted, and the results are exposed in Figs.6 and 7. From these last figures, it could be conjectured that **MD** do seem to follow a model similar to Eq.4.4, although not quite exactly.

Figure 5. Comparison of Eq.4.4 with the CDF of MD

Figure 6. Confidence bands at 99.9% of the fitted parameters $a \approx 4.6203$, $b \approx 0.03$ to the model $1 - \left(\frac{\sin \pi ax}{\pi bx}\right)^2$

Figure 7. Residuals of the model $1 - \frac{0.03 \sin^2(4.6203x)}{x^2}$

5. Entropy

In this work, the entropy of a random variable is considered to be the average level of "surprise", or "information" inherent to the variable's possible outcomes Wikipedia contributors 2023.

Given a discrete random variable X , which takes values in the alphabet \mathcal{X} and is distributed according to $p : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow [0, 1]$:

$$H(X) := - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} p(x) \log p(x) = \mathbb{E}[-\log p(X)], \tag{13}$$

It is conjectured that Low-Discrepancy Sequences contain "just enough" information for integration, as opposite of a numerical scheme that requires partitioning the interval at regular intervals (less "surprise") or a Monte Carlo scheme, that requires many functional evaluations (more "surprise"). In Table 4 the values of entropies for several numerical system is presented. Notice that **Md** occupy a relative intermediate position

concerning the numerical value of its Shannon entropy.

Table 4. Entropies of selected sequences

H(x) (entropy, or "degree of surprise")	Set measured
0	(no surprise, like a crystal, no choice) The first million differences between random integers in the range 1 to One million
0	(no surprise, like a crystal, no choice) The first million differences between random reals in the range 1 to One million
0.30103	(This is the flipping of a coin one million times)
0.30103	The first million digits of Pi
0.30103	The first million digits of E
0.30103	the first million digits of Sqrt[71]
0.778151	(rolling of one dice)
1.26895	The difference between the first million primes
1.63164	The difference of exponents of the first 47 Mersenne Primes
1.6721	The exponent of the first 47 Mersenne Primes
2.13791	Metadistances 6,6
2.89478	(Entropy of "fiery" poem (Blake 1793), 20 words)
2.99573	(entropy of a random choice of 20 common words)
3.00911	(entropy of poem "no man is an Island" (Donne 1623), 79 words)
4.36945	(entropy of random choice of common words, 79 words)
5.75118	(entropy of a million random integers in the range 1 to one million)
5.86415	(entropy of a million random integers in the range minus one million to one million)
6	(entropy of a million random reals in the range minus one million to one million)
6	the first million primes

This recent numerical findings and its relationship to **Md** are supported by previous analytic work Ortiz-Tapia and Støleum 2016.

6. Conclusion

A revision of previous work was performed, to find new evidence that \mathbf{Md} are an Equidistributed Sequence. It was conjectured that Ramanujan's master theorem serves as better argument for explaining the convergence of the solution while making numerical quadratures. The new statistics about previous results, show that \mathbf{Md} has the most symmetrical distribution of errors, and the least amount of extreme outliers for obtaining a result.

The \mathbf{Md} comply with all the equidistribution measures here studied, thus confirming this set as a Low-Discrepancy Sequence and an Equidistributed Sequence; the reason *why* they are equidistributed it is conjectured may be related to the equidistribution of the zeros of Riemann's zeta function, and some numerical evidence is presented to show statistical similarities with the GUE model.

Finally, it is show a comparison of the entropy for several numerical systems or encoding, whereupon \mathbf{Md} results having an intermediate level of entropy, possibly suggesting that \mathbf{Md} have the "right" amount of information for numerical quadrature, as opposite to the amount of information required for Monte Carlo or other numerical methods.

Competing Interests None.

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